

EBFMC25-OOP-20 · Neonatal Non-Conducted Premature Atrial Complexes: A Rare Cause of Severe Bradyarrhythmia and Hemodynamic Instability

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Arrhythmias in the neonatal period can range from benign rhythm disturbances to life-threatening arrhythmias, and, in some cases, can lead to severe hemodynamic disturbances and low cardiac output (Ban, 2017; Dubin, 2000). Non-conducted premature atrial complexes (PAC) are rare rhythm disturbances that can be confused with atrioventricular (AV) block but have a different mechanism (Liu & Peng, 2024). This condition, which can cause severe bradycardia and secondary cardiomyopathy, may pose a significant challenge in terms of diagnosis and management in neonatal intensive care unit patients. In this study, we evaluated the clinical course, treatment processes, and longterm outcomes of five patients with non-conducted PAC who were followed up for bradycardia.

Materials and Methods: Five patients with bradycardia and non-conducted PAC detected by electrocardiography (ECG) in the neonatal intensive care unit between 2017 and 2024 were retrospectively analyzed. Demographic data, ECG and Holter results, echocardiographic findings, treatments (propafenone, amiodarone), and long-term follow-up results were evaluated. Cardiac functions were examined by echocardiography, and treatment responses of the patients were analyzed.

Results: Bradycardia resolved with propafenone treatment in four of five patients and with amiodarone treatment in one patient. The Brugada pattern developed in two patients treated with propafenone, and their treatment was switched to amiodarone; the Brugada pattern disappeared within 48 hours (Ari & Ekici, 2017). During the period of non-conducted PAC, heart rates ranged between 45 and 65 beats per minute. Left ventricular systolic dysfunction secondary to bradycardia developed in three patients, but ventricular function returned to normal after treatment. Medical treatment was terminated in four patients within 12 months, and one patient was planned to be terminated at 12 months. During the follow-up period, no recurrence of bradycardia was observed in any patient, and isolated supraventricular premature beats were detected in <10% of the patients' Holter recordings.

Conclusion: In the neonatal period, non-conducted PAC can lead to severe bradycardia and hemodynamic disturbances (Ergül, 2017). This condition can be successfully managed with early diagnosis and appropriate antiarrhythmic therapy, and ventricular function can be normalized. However, caution should be exercised during propafenone treatment because of the risk of the Brugada pattern development. Our study aims to contribute to the diagnosis and treatment of non-conducted PAC in the neonatal period.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Non-conducted premature atrial complex, bradycardia, newborn, propafenone, brugada

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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